

CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT CHALLENGES OF TEACHER'S AND ITS EFFECT TO LEARNERS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN SAN ANDRES DISTRICT, DIVISION OF QUEZON: BASIS FOR A PROPOSED INTERVENTION PLAN

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the classroom management challenges faced by teachers in the San Andres District and their effect on learners' academic performance, culminating in the design of an intervention plan. Using a descriptive comparative research design, the study examined nine areas of classroom management: classroom rules and expectations, classroom discipline practices, teaching strategies utilized, availability of instructional support, classroom layout and physical environment, student behavior management, conflict management and resolution techniques, learner motivation and engagement, and cultural sensitivity and inclusiveness. Academic performance was assessed through the General Weighted Average (GWA) of 354 learners, while regression analysis determined the effect of teacher challenges on student outcomes. A total of 439 participants, comprising 85 teachers and 354 learners from Grades 1 to 6, were selected through stratified random sampling to ensure representative coverage. Findings revealed that teachers consistently perceive classroom management challenges as highly to very highly challenging, with cultural sensitivity, inclusiveness, and behavior management presenting the greatest difficulties. Learners demonstrated a mean GWA of 86.44 (SD = 6.62), reflecting a Very Satisfactory level of academic performance, though some students required targeted support to ensure equitable outcomes. Regression analysis indicated a statistically significant negative relationship between classroom management challenges and learner performance ($B = -2.552$, $\beta = -0.123$, $p = 0.020$), suggesting that increased teacher difficulties are associated with lower student GWA, albeit with a modest effect. Based on these findings, a comprehensive Intervention Plan was proposed to strengthen teachers' classroom management skills, foster inclusive and engaging learning environments, and enhance academic outcomes. The study highlights the critical role of teacher competencies, professional development, and culturally responsive practices in promoting effective teaching and student success.

Keywords: *Classroom Management, Teacher Challenges, Learner Performance, Professional Development*

INTRODUCTION

Teachers play a vital role in shaping learners' academic success and holistic development, with effective classroom management widely recognized as a fundamental component of quality education. It directly influences student behavior, engagement, and academic performance. As classrooms become increasingly diverse and inclusive, teachers are expected to implement structured, adaptive, and student-centered management strategies. This growing demand highlights the importance of well-managed classrooms in promoting positive learning environments and reducing disparities in educational outcomes (Burden, 2025; Cheon, Reeve, & Vansteenkiste, 2020).

Globally, classroom management is strengthened through teacher training, technology integration, and supportive policy frameworks that promote inclusive and learner-centered practices (De Villa & Manalo, 2020; Ozen & Yıldırım, 2020; Castroverde & Acala, 2021). However, in many developing contexts, teachers continue to face challenges such as overcrowding, limited resources, and inconsistent discipline systems, which negatively affect instructional effectiveness and student achievement (Cho, Mansfield, & Claughton, 2020; Yonas, Rupia, & Onyango, 2023).

In the Philippines, particularly in geographically isolated areas like San Andres District in the Division of Quezon, teachers handle multigrade classes, limited instructional materials, and diverse learner needs. These conditions often result in classroom management difficulties that may influence learners' academic performance.

Literature identifies key classroom management challenges, including student misbehavior, unclear rules, weak discipline practices, low motivation, and limited instructional resources (Bennett, 2022; Martin, 2023; Minero, 2023; Ugwoke, Okeke, & Ugwoke, 2022). Forghani-Arani, Cerna, and Bannon (2019) further emphasized that managing culturally diverse classrooms requires inclusivity and cultural competence, while Moore (2020) and Minero (2023) highlighted the importance of empathy and strong teacher–student relationships in improving engagement and behavior.

Instructional strategies and teacher preparedness are also critical. Killen and O'Toole (2023) stressed that differentiated and reflective teaching enhances learning outcomes, while Isma'il and Lukman (2022) and Ayoti (2023) found that adequate instructional materials improve student performance. Conversely, Cayabas Jr. and Sumeg-ang (2023) noted that resource limitations hinder effective instruction. Valencia et al. (2025) and Bandala and Diocos (2024) emphasized that well-organized physical environments support focus, discipline, and engagement.

Behavior management is influenced by learners' socio-emotional and motivational factors (Brandmiller, Dumont, & Becker, 2020). Agapito (2024), Dem Jhen (2024), and Mangulabnan, Dela Rosa, and Vargas (2021) highlighted the importance of training, mediation strategies, and leadership support in resolving classroom conflicts effectively. Likewise, Agregado and Gaitano (2024) and Barotas and Palma (2023) emphasized that learner motivation and engagement significantly affect academic performance.

Strong leadership and structured school systems further contribute to effective classroom management and learner achievement. Tan (2022) found that leadership fosters collaboration, teacher development, and improved learning environments. Killen and O'Toole (2023) and Brandmiller et al. (2020) also confirmed that classroom management directly affects instructional time, engagement, and academic outcomes.

Despite these findings, gaps remain in localized research focusing on rural contexts such as San Andres District, where cultural diversity, resource limitations, and multigrade settings intensify classroom management challenges. Most existing interventions are generalized and do not fully capture these contextual realities.

Thus, this study aims to examine the classroom management challenges of teachers in San Andres District and determine their effect on learners' academic performance. It specifically focuses on classroom discipline, instructional strategies, learner motivation, conflict management, resource availability, and cultural responsiveness. Ultimately, the study seeks to develop a localized intervention plan to strengthen classroom management practices and improve learners' academic outcomes in the Division of Quezon.

Research Questions

This study determined the classroom management challenges faced by teachers and their effects on learners' academic performance, serving as the basis for a proposed Intervention Plan. Specifically, it sought to address the following questions:

1. What are the classroom management challenges faced by teachers in San Andres District in terms of:
 - 1.1 Classroom Rules and Expectations;
 - 1.2 Classroom Discipline Practices;
 - 1.3 Teaching Strategies Utilized;
 - 1.4 Availability of Instructional Support;
 - 1.5 Classroom Layout and Physical Environment;
 - 1.6 Student Behavior Management;
 - 1.7 Conflict Management and Resolution Techniques;
 - 1.8 Learner Motivation and Engagement;
 - 1.9 Cultural Sensitivity and Inclusiveness?
2. What is the learners' academic performance as reflected in their progress report cards through the general weighted average?
3. Is there a significant effect of the classroom management challenges of teachers on the learners' academic performance as reflected in their progress report cards through the general weighted average?
4. Based on the findings of the study, what Intervention Plan can be proposed to address teachers' classroom management challenges?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive-comparative research design to examine the classroom management challenges of teachers and their effect on learners' academic performance in the San Andres District, Division of Quezon. This design was appropriate as it describes existing conditions without manipulation and allows comparison of variables to determine relationships and differences (Siedlecki, 2020). The study specifically identified teachers' classroom management challenges and analyzed how these influence learners' academic performance, serving as a basis for a proposed Intervention Plan. The study was conducted in the San Andres District, a rural and diverse municipality characterized by limited resources, large class sizes, and socio-economically varied learners. These contextual factors affect classroom management and student learning outcomes, making the locale suitable for the investigation. The respondents included 85 teachers and 354 learners from Grades 1 to 6, totaling 439 participants. Stratified random sampling and Cochran's formula were used to ensure proportional representation across grade levels. This allowed balanced analysis of classroom management challenges and academic performance variations. A researcher-made survey instrument was utilized, consisting of three parts: classroom management challenges, learners' academic performance (GWA), and perceived effects of challenges. The instrument was validated by experts and pilot-tested for reliability. Data were gathered through formal permissions, administered questionnaires, and retrieval of school records. Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were used to describe challenges and performance levels, while regression analysis determined the significant effect of classroom management challenges on learners' academic performance at a 0.05 level of significance. Ethical standards, including informed consent, confidentiality, and voluntary participation, were strictly observed throughout the study.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Table 1

Classroom Management Challenges Faced by Teachers in San Andres District in terms of Classroom Rules and Expectations

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. I often struggle to consistently enforce classroom rules because some students do not take them seriously, especially when there is a lack of support from their parents or guardians.	4.32	0.82	Very Highly Challenging
2. It's challenging for me to set clear expectations at the start of the school year, especially when students come from different backgrounds with varying levels of understanding of proper classroom behavior.	4.02	0.89	Highly Challenging

3. I find it difficult to maintain fairness and consistency in applying rules, particularly when dealing with learners who have behavioral issues or special needs.	4.38	0.91	Very Highly Challenging
4. Sometimes, I feel unsure whether my classroom rules are effective because students still exhibit disruptive behavior despite repeated reminders and interventions.	4.95	0.21	Very Highly Challenging
5. I face the challenge of balancing strict enforcement of rules with creating a warm and supportive classroom climate where students feel safe to express themselves.	4.73	0.62	Very Highly Challenging
Total	4.48	0.48	Very Highly Challenging

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 *Very Highly Challenging*, 3.40 – 4.19 *Highly Challenging*, 2.60 – 3.39, *Moderately Challenging*, 1.80 – 2.59 *Least Challenge*, 1.00 – 1.79 *Not a Challenge at All*

Table 1 presents the classroom management challenges experienced by teachers in San Andres District in terms of classroom rules and expectations. The overall mean of 4.48 (SD = 0.48) indicates that teachers perceive these challenges as Very Highly Challenging. The relatively low standard deviation suggests a strong agreement among teachers, indicating that these challenges are commonly experienced across the district rather than being isolated cases.

It can be noted from the data that teachers encounter significant difficulties in implementing classroom rules. Among the indicators, the highest mean was recorded for feeling unsure about the effectiveness of classroom rules (M = 4.95, SD = 0.21), which is interpreted as Very Highly Challenging. The very low standard deviation (0.21) on this item indicates a near-universal consensus among teachers, suggesting that uncertainty about rule effectiveness is a widespread and systemic concern rather than an individual issue. This highlights the need for clearer, more structured, and evidence-based approaches to classroom rule-setting and implementation.

Similarly, balancing strict enforcement of rules with maintaining a warm and supportive classroom climate (M = 4.73, SD = 0.62) was also rated as Very Highly Challenging, with a moderately low SD indicating general agreement among respondents. Maintaining fairness and consistency in applying rules (M = 4.38, SD = 0.91) and enforcing rules amid diverse learner behaviors (M = 4.32, SD = 0.82) also posed significant challenges; however, the relatively higher SD values suggest some variability in teachers' experiences, possibly due to differences in classroom context, learner profiles, and teaching strategies. Meanwhile, setting clear expectations at the beginning of the school year (M = 4.02, SD = 0.89), although still rated as Highly Challenging, obtained the lowest mean, with a higher SD indicating differing levels of difficulty among teachers.

The findings of this study align with the research of Ugwoke, Okeke, and Ugwoke (2022), which identified classroom management issues such as disrespect, inattentiveness, and poor discipline as major obstacles to effective teaching, often influenced by limited parental support and challenging home environments. This supports the present findings, particularly in relation to difficulties in rule enforcement and consistency. Furthermore, the emphasis on balancing discipline with a supportive classroom environment resonates with the framework of Pavidis (2023), who highlighted the importance of fostering positive classroom communities. Similarly, Owens et al. (2020) emphasized the need for professional development and targeted interventions to strengthen teachers' classroom management competencies.

Hence, the results in Table 1 underscore the need for systematic training, strengthened parental involvement, and the adoption of evidence-based classroom management strategies. Addressing the strong consensus on key challenges, particularly the effectiveness of classroom rules, is essential in helping teachers create structured, fair, and supportive learning environments that promote positive student behavior and improved academic outcomes.

Table 5
Classroom Management Challenges Faced by Teachers in San Andres District in terms of Classroom Discipline Practices

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. I find it difficult to manage student misbehavior consistently, especially when the disciplinary policies in school are unclear or not strictly implemented.	3.68	1.01	Highly Challenging
2. I often hesitate to apply certain disciplinary actions because I fear they may be misinterpreted by students, parents, or even administrators.	4.75	0.60	Very Highly Challenging
3. Dealing with repeated offenses by the same students can be exhausting, and sometimes I feel like my strategies are no longer effective.	3.79	0.96	Highly Challenging
4. I struggle to find the right balance between being firm and being compassionate when disciplining students with emotional or behavioral concerns.	4.46	0.89	Very Highly Challenging
5. It's challenging for me to handle disciplinary issues when I feel unsupported or when consequences are not followed through at the school level.	3.46	0.75	Highly Challenging
Total	4.03	0.59	Highly Challenging

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 *Very Highly Challenging*, 3.40 – 4.19 *Highly Challenging*, 2.60 – 3.39, *Moderately Challenging*, 1.80 – 2.59 *Least Challenge*, 1.00 – 1.79 *Not a Challenge at All*

Table 2 presents the classroom management challenges encountered by teachers in San Andres District in terms of classroom discipline practices. The overall mean of 4.03 (SD = 0.59) indicates that teachers perceive these challenges as Highly Challenging, suggesting that discipline-related concerns significantly affect classroom management, though slightly less intensely than those related to classroom rules and expectations. The relatively low standard deviation implies a general agreement among teachers regarding the presence of these challenges.

It can be noted from the data that teachers experience varying levels of difficulty in managing discipline practices. The highest mean was recorded for hesitation in applying certain disciplinary actions due to fear of misinterpretation by students, parents, or administrators (M = 4.75, SD = 0.60), which is interpreted as Very Highly Challenging. While the challenge is notably high, the slightly higher standard deviation (0.60) compared to other highly rated items suggests some variation in teachers' experiences, indicating that not all teachers feel equally hesitant in applying disciplinary actions. This variation may be influenced by differences in confidence levels, prior experiences, or the level of support received from school leadership.

Similarly, finding the right balance between being firm and compassionate (M = 4.46, SD = 0.89) is also Very Highly Challenging, with a higher SD indicating diverse experiences among teachers. Other indicators, such as dealing with repeated offenses (M = 3.79, SD = 0.96) and managing misbehavior under unclear policies (M = 3.68, SD = 1.01), also reflect Highly Challenging conditions, but their relatively higher SD values suggest greater variability, possibly due to differences in classroom context and policy implementation. Meanwhile, handling disciplinary issues when support is lacking (M = 3.46, SD = 0.75) obtained the lowest mean, though still within the Highly Challenging range.

The findings of this study are consistent with Forghani-Arani, Cerna, and Bannon (2019), who emphasized that managing diverse classrooms is particularly challenging due to cultural and linguistic differences. Their study highlights the importance of inclusivity and cultural understanding, aligning with the present findings on teachers' struggles to apply discipline fairly and compassionately. Additionally, the results support Yonas, Rupia, and Onyango (2023), who identified disruptive behavior, large class sizes, and limited resources as key factors affecting discipline practices. The reported lack of support and unclear disciplinary procedures further reinforces that these challenges are both classroom-level and systemic in nature.

Hence, the findings suggest that addressing classroom discipline challenges in San Andres District requires clear and consistently enforced school policies, strengthened administrative support, culturally responsive practices, and continuous professional development. These measures can help teachers confidently implement fair, consistent, and effective disciplinary strategies that promote positive student behavior and a conducive learning environment.

Table 3

Classroom Management Challenges Faced by Teachers in San Andres District in terms of Teaching Strategies Utilized

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. I sometimes struggle to choose the most effective teaching strategy that fits the diverse learning styles of my students.	4.21	0.79	Very Highly Challenging
2. I find it challenging to keep students engaged, especially when the lessons require approaches that are beyond traditional lecture methods.	4.64	0.70	Highly Challenging
3. I want to try more innovative strategies, but limited resources and time often prevent me from fully implementing them.	3.61	0.67	Very Highly Challenging
4. It's hard to manage the class when a teaching strategy that worked for one group of learners doesn't work for another.	4.01	0.73	Highly Challenging
5. I feel uncertain about how to effectively modify or differentiate my teaching strategies to address the varied academic levels in my classroom.	4.92	0.32	Very Highly Challenging
Total	4.28	0.41	Very Highly Challenging

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 *Very Highly Challenging*, 3.40 – 4.19 *Highly Challenging*, 2.60 – 3.39 *Moderately Challenging*, 1.80 – 2.59 *Least Challenge*, 1.00 – 1.79 *Not a Challenge at All*

Table 3 presents the classroom management challenges encountered by teachers in San Andres District in terms of the teaching strategies utilized. The overall mean of 4.28 (SD = 0.41) indicates that teachers perceive these challenges as Very Highly Challenging. The relatively low standard deviation suggests a strong consensus among teachers, implying that difficulties related to teaching strategies are widely experienced across the district.

It can be noted from the data that teachers face significant challenges in selecting and implementing appropriate instructional strategies. The highest mean was recorded for uncertainty in modifying or differentiating teaching strategies to address varied academic levels (M = 4.92, SD = 0.32), interpreted as Very Highly Challenging. The very low SD (0.32) indicates a strong agreement among teachers, suggesting that this concern is nearly universal and highlights a critical need for support in differentiated instruction. Similarly, keeping students engaged, especially when lessons require approaches beyond traditional methods (M = 4.64, SD = 0.70), is also Very Highly Challenging, with moderate variability in teachers' experiences.

Other indicators, such as choosing the most effective strategy for diverse learning styles (M = 4.21, SD = 0.79) and managing classes when strategies do not work uniformly across groups (M = 4.01, SD = 0.73), reflect Highly Challenging conditions with noticeable variation, indicating that teachers' experiences differ depending on classroom context and learner diversity. Meanwhile, trying innovative strategies despite limited resources and time (M = 3.61, SD = 0.67) obtained the lowest mean, though still within the Highly Challenging range, with a moderate SD suggesting some differences in access to resources and opportunities for innovation.

The findings strongly support the assertions of Killen and O'Toole (2023), who emphasized that effective teaching depends on the use of varied instructional approaches aligned with learners' needs. Their advocacy for reflective teaching and differentiated instruction aligns with the challenges identified in this study, particularly in addressing diverse learning styles and academic levels. Moreover, the results highlight that limited resources and time constraints hinder the implementation of innovative strategies, reinforcing the close relationship between instructional practices and classroom management.

Hence, the findings suggest that addressing these challenges requires continuous professional development in differentiated and student-centered instruction, along with improved access to instructional resources and stronger administrative support. These efforts will enable teachers to implement more effective teaching strategies, enhance student engagement, and create a more conducive learning environment.

Table 4
Classroom Management Challenges Faced by Teachers in San Andres District in terms of Availability of Instructional Support

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. I often struggle to deliver effective lessons because of the lack of instructional materials in our school.	4.87	0.53	Very Highly Challenging
2. I feel limited in applying creative teaching strategies due to the unavailability of updated learning resources.	4.48	0.80	Very Highly Challenging
3. I find myself spending my own money to purchase teaching aids just to support my classroom needs.	3.88	0.94	Highly Challenging
4. I sometimes feel unmotivated when the instructional tools I need are either outdated or insufficient.	3.55	0.85	Highly Challenging
5. I face difficulties managing my class when I don't have the appropriate materials to cater to different learners' needs.	4.82	0.56	Very Highly Challenging
Total	4.32	0.49	Very Highly Challenging

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 *Very Highly Challenging*, 3.40 – 4.19 *Highly Challenging*, 2.60 – 3.39, *Moderately Challenging*, 1.80 – 2.59 *Least Challenge*, 1.00 – 1.79 *Not a Challenge at All*

Table 4 illustrates the classroom management challenges of teachers in San Andres District in terms of the availability of instructional support. The overall mean of 4.32 (SD = 0.49) indicates that teachers perceive these challenges as Very Highly Challenging. The relatively low standard deviation suggests a strong agreement among teachers, implying that limited instructional support is a common and widespread issue across the district.

It can be noted from the data that teachers experience serious difficulties due to the lack of instructional resources. The highest mean was recorded for struggling to deliver effective lessons due to insufficient instructional materials (M = 4.87, SD = 0.53), interpreted as Very Highly Challenging. The low SD indicates a high level of consensus, suggesting that this concern is consistently experienced by most teachers. Similarly, difficulties in managing the class without appropriate materials for diverse learners (M = 4.82, SD = 0.56) also reflect Very Highly Challenging conditions, with minimal variation in responses.

Moreover, feeling limited in applying creative teaching strategies due to the lack of updated resources (M = 4.48, SD = 0.80) is also Very Highly Challenging, though the slightly higher SD suggests some variation in access to or utilization of available materials. Spending personal funds for teaching aids (M = 3.88, SD = 0.94) and feeling unmotivated due to outdated or insufficient tools (M = 3.55, SD = 0.85) are rated as Highly Challenging, with relatively higher SD values indicating differing experiences among teachers, possibly influenced by school context or available support systems.

The findings resonate with Isma'il and Lukman (2022), who emphasized that access to quality instructional resources enhances teaching effectiveness and student performance. Similarly, Ayoti (2023) identified a strong positive relationship between the use of instructional media and improved learning outcomes. The study of Cayabas Jr. and Sumeg-ang (2023) further supports these findings, highlighting that public school teachers often face challenges in developing and utilizing instructional materials due to limited resources and insufficient training.

Hence, the results underscore that adequate instructional support is a critical component of effective classroom management. The strong consensus on key challenges, particularly the lack of instructional materials, highlights the need for prioritized resource allocation, provision of updated learning materials, and continuous teacher training. Addressing these concerns can significantly enhance teaching effectiveness, improve student engagement, and promote better classroom management outcomes.

Table 5

Classroom Management Challenges Faced by Teachers in San Andres District in terms of Classroom Layout and Physical Environment

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. I find it hard to manage student behavior when my classroom is overcrowded and lacks proper space for movement.	3.64	0.57	Highly Challenging
2. I struggle to implement group activities effectively because the classroom furniture is not conducive to flexible seating arrangements.	4.42	0.98	Very Highly Challenging
3. I often feel that the physical setup of my room limits student engagement and collaboration.	3.62	0.72	Highly Challenging
4. I get frustrated when the poor lighting and ventilation in my classroom affect my students' concentration and comfort.	4.80	0.59	Highly Challenging
5. I feel constrained in organizing interactive learning stations due to the limited and fixed layout of the classroom.	4.85	0.52	Very Highly Challenging
Total	4.27	0.46	Very Highly Challenging

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 *Very Highly Challenging*, 3.40 – 4.19 *Highly Challenging*, 2.60 – 3.39, *Moderately Challenging*, 1.80 – 2.59 *Least Challenge*, 1.00 – 1.79 *Not a Challenge at All*

Table 5 presents the classroom management challenges of teachers in San Andres District in terms of classroom layout and physical environment. The overall mean of 4.27 (SD = 0.46) indicates that these challenges are perceived as Very Highly Challenging. The relatively low standard deviation suggests a strong consensus among teachers, implying that issues related to the physical environment are commonly experienced across schools.

It can be noted from the data that teachers face significant constraints due to classroom layout and environmental conditions. The highest mean was recorded for feeling constrained in organizing interactive learning stations due to limited and fixed classroom layouts (M = 4.85, SD = 0.52), interpreted as Very Highly Challenging. The low SD indicates that this concern is widely shared among teachers, highlighting a systemic limitation in classroom design. Similarly, frustration caused by poor lighting and ventilation (M = 4.80, SD = 0.59) is also a major concern, with relatively consistent responses among teachers.

Moreover, difficulty in implementing group activities due to non-flexible furniture (M = 4.42, SD = 0.98) is rated as Very Highly Challenging, but the higher SD suggests greater variability in teachers' experiences, possibly reflecting differences in classroom facilities across schools. Other indicators, such as managing behavior in overcrowded

classrooms (M = 3.64, SD = 0.57) and limitations in student engagement and collaboration due to physical setup (M = 3.62, SD = 0.72), are considered Highly Challenging, with moderate variation indicating that these issues may depend on class size and room conditions.

The findings are consistent with Valencia et al. (2025), who emphasized that a well-organized classroom environment enhances learner focus and supports effective classroom management. Likewise, Bandala and Diocos (2024) highlight that proper management of physical space plays a crucial role in promoting positive student behavior and engagement. These studies, together with the present findings, affirm that the physical environment is a critical factor influencing both teaching effectiveness and student learning.

Hence, the results suggest that improving classroom layout, ensuring adequate space, and providing better lighting and ventilation are essential in addressing classroom management challenges. Enhancing the physical learning environment can support interactive teaching strategies, improve student engagement, and create a more conducive atmosphere for learning.

Table 6
Classroom Management Challenges Faced by Teachers in San Andres District in terms of Student Behavior Management

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. I often struggle to maintain order in the classroom when students display disruptive behaviors.	3.33	0.70	Highly Challenging
2. I find it difficult to apply consistent discipline strategies, especially when managing a class with diverse behavior issues.	3.82	0.64	Highly Challenging
3. I feel overwhelmed when students don't respond positively to my efforts in correcting their misbehavior.	4.65	0.67	Very Highly Challenging
4. I sometimes lose instructional time because I have to constantly address behavioral problems.	4.45	0.89	Very Highly Challenging
5. I find it challenging to establish mutual respect and positive behavior without adequate support or training.	4.05	0.65	Highly Challenging
Total	4.06	0.41	Highly Challenging

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 *Very Highly Challenging*, 3.40 – 4.19 *Highly Challenging*, 2.60 – 3.39, *Moderately Challenging*, 1.80 – 2.59 *Least Challenge*, 1.00 – 1.79 *Not a Challenge at All*

Table 9 examines the classroom management challenges of teachers in San Andres District in terms of student behavior management. The overall mean of 4.06 (SD = 0.41) indicates that these challenges are perceived as Highly Challenging. The relatively low standard deviation suggests a strong level of agreement among teachers, implying that behavior-related issues are commonly experienced across classrooms.

It can be noted from the data that teachers encounter varying degrees of difficulty in managing student behavior. The highest mean was recorded for feeling overwhelmed when students do not respond positively to corrective efforts (M = 4.65, SD = 0.67), interpreted as Very Highly Challenging, with moderate variation indicating differences in teachers' coping strategies and classroom contexts. Similarly, losing instructional time due to frequent behavioral disruptions (M = 4.45, SD = 0.89) is also Very Highly Challenging, though the higher SD suggests that some teachers experience this issue more intensely than others. Other indicators, such as establishing mutual respect and positive behavior without adequate support (M = 4.05, SD = 0.65) and applying consistent discipline strategies for diverse behaviors (M = 3.82, SD = 0.64), are rated as Highly Challenging, with relatively consistent responses among teachers.

Meanwhile, maintaining order when students display disruptive behaviors (M = 3.33, SD = 0.70) obtained the lowest mean, though still within the Moderately to Highly Challenging range, with moderate variation suggesting differences in classroom management skills or student behavior profiles. The variation across indicators reflects that while behavior management is a shared concern, the intensity of these challenges may depend on factors such as class composition, teacher experience, and available support systems.

The findings align with Brandmiller, Dumont, and Becker (2020), who emphasized that teachers' perceptions of student behavior are influenced by learners' motivation, abilities, and socio-emotional characteristics. Their study highlights the importance of proactive and student-centered behavior management approaches to address individual differences and promote inclusive classroom environments.

Hence, the results underscore that student behavior management remains a critical aspect of classroom management that requires consistent strategies, targeted interventions, and strong institutional support. Enhancing teachers' skills in behavior management, along with providing adequate training and resources, can help reduce disruptions, maximize instructional time, and foster a more positive and respectful learning environment.

Classroom Management Challenges Faced by Teachers in San Andres District in terms of Conflict Management and Resolution Techniques

Table 7 focuses on the classroom management challenges related to conflict management and resolution techniques among teachers in San Andres District. The overall mean of 4.34 (SD = 0.55) indicates that this aspect is perceived as Very Highly

Challenging. The moderate standard deviation suggests a general agreement among teachers, although slight variations in experiences exist depending on individual skills and classroom contexts.

Table 7
Classroom Management Challenges Faced by Teachers in San Andres District in terms of Conflict Management and Resolution Techniques

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. I often find it challenging to mediate conflicts between students without escalating the situation further.	3.64	0.57	Highly Challenging
2. I struggle to apply effective conflict resolution strategies when disagreements disrupt classroom harmony.	4.42	1.00	Very Highly Challenging
3. I feel unprepared to handle emotionally charged confrontations among learners.	4.46	0.81	Very Highly Challenging
4. I find it difficult to remain neutral when addressing conflicts that involve personal student issues.	4.46	0.92	Very Highly Challenging
5. I lack adequate training in conflict resolution, which affects my ability to maintain a peaceful classroom environment.	4.74	0.66	Very Highly Challenging
Total	4.34	0.55	Very Highly Challenging

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 *Very Highly Challenging*, 3.40 – 4.19 *Highly Challenging*, 2.60 – 3.39, *Moderately Challenging*, 1.80 – 2.59 *Least Challenge*, 1.00 – 1.79 *Not a Challenge at All*

It can be noted from the data that teachers experience considerable difficulty in managing and resolving conflicts effectively. The highest mean was recorded for lack of adequate training in conflict resolution (M = 4.74, SD = 0.66), interpreted as Very Highly Challenging, with relatively consistent responses indicating that this is a common concern among teachers. Similarly, feeling unprepared to handle emotionally charged confrontations (M = 4.46, SD = 0.81) and difficulty in remaining neutral during conflicts involving personal student issues (M = 4.46, SD = 0.92) are also Very Highly Challenging, with higher SD values suggesting variability in teachers' confidence and experience in managing such situations.

Moreover, struggling to apply effective conflict resolution strategies when disagreements disrupt classroom harmony (M = 4.42, SD = 1.00) reflects a Very Highly Challenging condition, with the highest SD indicating notable differences in teachers' abilities or access to training and support. Meanwhile, mediating conflicts without escalating the situation (M = 3.64, SD = 0.57) obtained the lowest mean, though still within the Highly Challenging range, with a lower SD suggesting more consistent experiences among teachers.

The findings are consistent with Agapito (2024), who emphasized the importance of structured training programs to enhance teachers' conflict management competencies. Similarly, Dem Jhen (2024) highlighted the use of practical strategies such as negotiation and peer mediation, while Mangulabnan, Dela Rosa, and Vargas (2021) noted that leadership support plays a crucial role in effective conflict resolution and overall school performance.

Hence, the results underscore that conflict management is a critical component of classroom management that requires targeted training, structured approaches, and strong institutional support. Strengthening teachers' skills in mediation, neutrality, and emotional management can help reduce classroom conflicts, promote positive relationships, and create a more conducive learning environment.

Table 8
Classroom Management Challenges Faced by Teachers in San Andres District in terms of Learner Motivation and Engagement

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. I sometimes find it difficult to address the diverse cultural backgrounds of my students in my lesson plans.	4.95	0.30	Very Highly Challenging
2. I struggle to create an inclusive environment where every learner feels respected and represented.	4.55	0.68	Very Highly Challenging
3. I am not always confident in handling culturally sensitive topics during classroom discussions.	4.96	0.19	Very Highly Challenging
4. I find it challenging to avoid unintentional bias when interacting with students from different cultural groups.	3.35	0.72	Highly Challenging
5. I need more support and training to promote cultural responsiveness and inclusivity in my teaching practices.	4.07	0.67	Highly Challenging
Total	4.38	0.25	Very Highly Challenging

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 *Very Highly Challenging*, 3.40 – 4.19 *Highly Challenging*, 2.60 – 3.39, *Moderately Challenging*, 1.80 – 2.59 *Least Challenge*, 1.00 – 1.79 *Not a Challenge at All*

Table 8 examines the classroom management challenges related to learner motivation and engagement among teachers in San Andres District. The overall mean of 4.38 (SD = 0.25) indicates that these challenges are perceived as Very Highly Challenging. The very low standard deviation suggests a strong consensus among teachers, implying that issues related to motivating and engaging learners particularly in diverse classroom contexts are widely experienced and consistent across respondents.

It can be noted from the data that teachers face significant challenges in addressing diversity and inclusivity in their classrooms. The highest means were recorded for handling culturally sensitive topics ($M = 4.96$, $SD = 0.19$) and addressing diverse cultural backgrounds in lesson planning ($M = 4.95$, $SD = 0.30$), both interpreted as Very Highly Challenging. The extremely low SD values for these indicators indicate near-universal agreement among teachers, highlighting that these concerns are systemic and require focused intervention. Similarly, creating an inclusive environment where every learner feels respected ($M = 4.55$, $SD = 0.68$) is also Very Highly Challenging, with moderate variation in teachers' experiences. Other indicators, such as the need for more support and training in promoting cultural responsiveness ($M = 4.07$, $SD = 0.67$) and avoiding unintentional bias ($M = 3.35$, $SD = 0.72$), are rated as Highly Challenging, with higher SD values suggesting variability in teachers' preparedness, awareness, and access to professional development. The variation implies that while some teachers may have developed inclusive practices, others still require substantial support. The findings align with Agregado and Gaitano (2024), who emphasized that learner motivation improves when teachers foster supportive relationships and recognize student efforts. Similarly, Barotas and Palma (2023) highlighted that increased motivation and engagement significantly influence academic performance and learning outcomes.

Hence, the results underscore that learner motivation and engagement, particularly in culturally diverse classrooms, remain critical challenges in classroom management. The strong consensus on key issues highlights the need for targeted training in culturally responsive pedagogy, inclusive teaching strategies, and bias awareness. Strengthening these areas can enhance student participation, promote equity, and create a more supportive and engaging learning environment.

Table 9
Classroom Management Challenges Faced by Teachers in San Andres District in terms of Cultural Sensitivity and Inclusiveness

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. I struggle to address diverse cultural norms and communication styles, which sometimes leads to misunderstandings and conflicts in my classroom.	4.46	0.75	Very Highly Challenging
2. My limited knowledge about my students' cultural backgrounds makes it difficult for me to create an inclusive learning environment that respects and celebrates their diversity.	4.92	0.41	Very Highly Challenging
3. I realize that some of the classroom rules and disciplinary practices I implement may unintentionally marginalize learners from minority or indigenous communities.	4.92	0.38	Very Highly Challenging
4. I face challenges with language barriers and the lack of culturally relevant instructional materials, which hinders effective classroom engagement and equal participation.	4.92	0.28	Very Highly Challenging
5. I find it difficult to balance uniform academic expectations with culturally responsive teaching strategies, which affects classroom harmony and student motivation.	4.36	0.96	Very Highly Challenging
Total	4.72	0.39	Very Highly Challenging

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 *Very Highly Challenging*, 3.40 – 4.19 *Highly Challenging*, 2.60 – 3.39, *Moderately Challenging*, 1.80 – 2.59 *Least Challenge*, 1.00 – 1.79 *Not a Challenge at All*

Table 12 presents the classroom management challenges of teachers in San Andres District in terms of cultural sensitivity and inclusiveness. The overall mean of 4.72 (SD = 0.39) indicates that these challenges are Very Highly Challenging. The low standard deviation suggests strong agreement among teachers, highlighting that difficulties in creating culturally responsive and inclusive classrooms are widely shared across the district.

It can be noted from the data that teachers experience significant challenges in addressing diversity and ensuring inclusiveness. The highest means were recorded for creating an inclusive environment that respects students' diverse cultural backgrounds (M = 4.92, SD = 0.41), recognizing and adjusting classroom rules or disciplinary practices that may marginalize learners from minority or indigenous communities (M = 4.92, SD = 0.38), and overcoming language barriers while using culturally relevant instructional materials (M = 4.92, SD = 0.28), all interpreted as Very Highly Challenging. The extremely low SDs indicate near-universal agreement, showing that these concerns are systemic rather than isolated to specific teachers or schools.

Other indicators, such as addressing diverse cultural norms and communication styles (M = 4.46, SD = 0.75) and balancing uniform academic expectations with culturally responsive teaching strategies (M = 4.36, SD = 0.96), are also Very Highly Challenging, with slightly higher SDs suggesting variation in teachers' confidence, experience, or access to resources to implement inclusive practices. The lowest mean was recorded for balancing uniform academic expectations with culturally responsive strategies (4.36), indicating this is a comparatively less challenging, yet still very significant, issue.

The findings align with Minero (2023), who emphasized that teachers' empathy and personal engagement help bridge emotional gaps, making students feel valued and motivated. Similarly, Moore (2020) highlighted that forming authentic relationships with students and understanding their cultural contexts are essential for effective instruction and classroom management.

Hence, Table 12 underscores that cultural sensitivity and inclusiveness are critical for effective classroom management. Addressing these challenges requires deliberate preparation, culturally responsive pedagogies, and strategies that foster an environment where all students feel respected, represented, and supported in their learning.

Table 10

Overall Classroom Management Challenges Faced by Teachers in San Andres District

Indicators	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. Classroom Rules and Expectations	85	4.48	.48	Very Highly Challenging
2. Classroom Discipline Practices	85	4.03	.59	Highly Challenging
3. Teaching Strategies Utilized	85	4.28	.41	Very Highly Challenging
4. Availability of Instructional Support	85	4.32	.49	Very Highly Challenging
5. Classroom Layout and Physical Environment	85	4.27	.46	Very Highly Challenging
6. Student Behavior Management	85	4.06	.41	Highly Challenging
7. Conflict Management and Resolution Techniques	85	4.34	.55	Very Highly Challenging
8. Learner Motivation and Engagement	85	4.38	.25	Very Highly Challenging
9. Cultural Sensitivity and Inclusiveness	85	4.72	.39	Very Highly Challenging
Overall	85	4.32	.32	Very Highly Challenging

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 *Very Highly Challenging*, 3.40 – 4.19 *Highly Challenging*, 2.60 – 3.39, *Moderately Challenging*, 1.80 – 2.59 *Least Challenge*, 1.00 – 1.79 *Not a Challenge at All*

Table 10 presents the overall classroom management challenges experienced by teachers in the San Andres District. The overall mean score of 4.32 (SD = 0.32) indicates that teachers generally experience classroom management practices at a very highly challenging level, suggesting that while strategies and systems are largely in place, notable challenges persist across multiple dimensions.

Among the indicators, Cultural Sensitivity and Inclusiveness (M = 4.72, SD = 0.39) received the highest mean score, indicating that teachers strongly recognize the importance of culturally responsive and inclusive practices. This aligns with Forghani-Arani, Cerna, and Bannon (2019), who emphasized that managing culturally diverse classrooms requires teachers to implement inclusive strategies and demonstrate cultural understanding. Similarly, Moore (2020) and Minero (2023) highlighted that authentic teacher–student relationships and empathy foster stronger engagement and classroom harmony.

Closely following this, Classroom Rules and Expectations (M = 4.48, SD = 0.48) and Learner Motivation and Engagement (M = 4.38, SD = 0.25) also received high

ratings. This indicates that teachers place strong emphasis on establishing clear expectations and motivating learners. Ugwoke, Okeke, and Ugwoke (2022) identified weak rule enforcement and inconsistent discipline as barriers to effective teaching, while Agregado and Gaitano (2024) emphasized that learner motivation improves when teachers foster supportive relationships and recognize student efforts.

The data reveal a clear triadic interconnection among these top three challenges. Teachers who struggle with cultural sensitivity and inclusiveness are more likely to face difficulties in setting fair and inclusive classroom rules and, consequently, may encounter challenges in motivating a diverse group of learners. In other words, a lack of cultural responsiveness can lead to perceptions of unfair or inconsistent classroom expectations, which may reduce learner engagement and motivation (Forghani-Arani et al., 2019; Moore, 2020; Minero, 2023). This finding underscores the need for a holistic professional development approach that simultaneously addresses cultural competence, classroom rule enforcement, and student engagement strategies.

Other indicators also highlight persistent challenges. Conflict Management and Resolution Techniques ($M = 4.34$, $SD = 0.55$) suggest that teachers frequently encounter interpersonal and behavioral conflicts in the classroom, supporting Agapito (2024), who emphasized structured grievance systems and targeted teacher training for effective conflict resolution. Mangulabnan, Dela Rosa, and Vargas (2021) similarly highlighted the role of school leadership in supporting teachers' conflict management capacity.

Teaching Strategies Utilized ($M = 4.28$, $SD = 0.41$) and Availability of Instructional Support ($M = 4.32$, $SD = 0.49$) indicate that while teachers employ varied instructional approaches, limitations in resources and training remain significant challenges. Killen and O'Toole (2023) stressed that effective classroom management is closely linked to differentiated and reflective teaching practices, and Isma'il and Lukman (2022), along with Ayoti (2023), found that adequate instructional resources enhance student performance and engagement. Similarly, Cayabas Jr. and Sumegang (2023) reported that insufficient materials and training constrain effective instruction.

Moderate ratings in Classroom Discipline Practices ($M = 4.03$, $SD = 0.59$) and Student Behavior Management ($M = 4.06$, $SD = 0.41$) highlight ongoing challenges in maintaining consistent discipline. Owens (2020) emphasized the need for targeted professional development to improve behavior management skills, while Brandmiller, Dumont, and Becker (2020) noted that learner motivation and socio-emotional factors influence teachers' perceptions of behavior, reinforcing the importance of student-centered management strategies.

While the Classroom Layout and Physical Environment ($M = 4.27$, $SD = 0.46$) also impacts management effectiveness. Valencia et al. (2025) discussed DepEd Order No. 21, s. 2023, emphasizing that organized classroom environments improve focus and cognitive clarity. Bandala and Diocos (2024) further highlighted that effective space management contributes to positive classroom experiences.

The findings collectively suggest that effective classroom management is multifaceted, requiring clear policies, culturally responsive practices, administrative support, professional development, and adequate resources. The strong interconnection among cultural sensitivity, classroom rules, and learner motivation emphasizes that interventions must be holistic. Focusing on one area without addressing the others may produce limited outcomes. A systemic approach integrating policy clarity, leadership support, ongoing teacher training, and learner-centered strategies is essential to sustaining positive, inclusive, and academically engaging classroom environments (Forghani-Arani et al., 2019; Agregado & Gaitano, 2024; Moore, 2020).

Part II. Learners' Academic Performance as Reflected in their Progress Report Cards through the General Weighted Average.

Table 11

Learners' Academic Performance as Reflected in their Progress Report Cards Through General Weighted Average

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
GWA	354	76	95	86.44%	6.62	Very Satisfactory

Table 11 presents the academic performance of 354 learners in the San Andres District as reflected in their General Weighted Average (GWA). The data show a minimum GWA of 76 and a maximum of 95, with a mean of 86.44 and a standard deviation of 6.62.

The mean score of 86.44 indicates that, on average, learners fall within the Very Satisfactory performance level based on the Department of Education's grading scale. This suggests that the majority of students are meeting, and in many cases exceeding, the expected curriculum standards. The relatively moderate standard deviation (6.62) indicates some variation in performance, but not extreme disparities, implying a generally consistent level of academic achievement across learners.

The wide range between the minimum (76) and maximum (95), however, reflects performance differences among students. While many learners are performing at very satisfactory to outstanding levels, some remain within the fairly satisfactory range. This highlights the need for sustained academic support programs to ensure equitable outcomes for all learners.

The findings align with the study of Tan and Lim (2022), who emphasized that effective school leadership positively influences student academic outcomes by promoting teacher collaboration, professional development, and supportive learning environments. Strong leadership and organized classroom management practices, as reflected in the previous findings, may contribute to the generally high academic performance observed in the district.

Furthermore, educational performance as measured by grades is widely recognized as a critical indicator of school effectiveness. As noted by Ballotpedia (2024), academic achievement metrics are commonly used to evaluate the success of educational programs and policy interventions. This underscores the importance of systematically monitoring learners' GWA to assess whether instructional strategies and classroom management practices translate into measurable academic gains.

In the Philippine context, the results are consistent with the goals of the DepEd Order No. 36, s. 2016 also known as Policy Guidelines on Awards and Recognition for K to 12 Basic Education Program in the Philippines, which operationalizes the K to 12 Basic Education Program. The policy emphasizes holistic learner development cognitive, affective, and psychomotor and aims to raise academic standards to meet global benchmarks. The high mean GWA suggests that learners in San Andres District are generally achieving the intended outcomes of the K to 12 curriculum frameworks.

Overall, the academic performance data indicate that learners in the district are largely successful in meeting curriculum expectations, with many achieving very satisfactory to outstanding results. However, the presence of learners at the lower end of the performance range calls for continued targeted interventions, differentiated instruction, and academic support programs. Maintaining high standards while ensuring inclusivity and equity will be essential in sustaining and further improving learner achievement across all grade levels.

Part III. Significant Effect of the Classroom Management Challenges of Teachers on the Learners' Academic Performance as Reflected in their Progress Report Cards through the General Weighted Average.

Table 12

Regression Analysis on the Testing of Significant Effect of the Classroom Management Challenges of Teachers on the Learners' Academic Performance as Reflected in their Progress Report Cards through the General Weighted Average.

Model Summary

R	R²	Adjusted R²	Std. Error of Estimate
0.123	0.015	0.012	6.57652

ANOVA Fit

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remarks
Regression	235.055	1	235.055	5.435	.020*	Significant
Residual	15224.199	352	43.251			
Total	15459.254	353				

Regression Coefficients

Predictor	B	Std. Error	Beta (β)	t	Sig.	Remarks
Constant	97.465	4.742	—	20.554	0	Significant
Classroom Management Challenges	-2.552	1.095	-0.123	-2.331	.020*	

Table 12 presents the regression analysis examining whether classroom management challenges significantly predict learners' academic performance as reflected in their General Weighted Average (GWA). In Model Summary Interpretation, the model shows an R value of 0.123, indicating a weak relationship between classroom management challenges and learners' academic performance. The R² value of 0.015 means that approximately 1.5% of the variance in learners' GWA can be explained by classroom management challenges. The Adjusted R² (0.012) confirms that the explanatory power of the model remains very small even after adjusting for sample size. Although the percentage of variance explained is minimal, the model still demonstrates a statistically measurable relationship.

While ANOVA results reveal an F-value of 5.435 with a significance level of 0.020, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that the regression model is statistically significant, meaning classroom management challenges significantly predict learners' academic performance.

On the other hand, the regression coefficient for classroom management challenges is B = -2.552, with a Beta (β) = -0.123, and a p-value of 0.020. The negative coefficient indicates an inverse relationship between the variables. This means that as classroom management challenges increase, learners' academic performance (GWA) tends to decrease.

Specifically, for every one-unit increase in classroom management challenges, the learners' GWA decreases by approximately 2.552 points, holding other factors constant. Although the effect size is small, it is statistically significant, suggesting that classroom management plays a meaningful role in influencing academic outcomes.

The findings are consistent with Killen and O'Toole (2023), who emphasized that effective instructional strategies and structured classroom environments directly contribute to improved academic achievement. When teachers struggle with management challenges, instructional flow is disrupted, which may negatively affect student learning outcomes.

Similarly, Brandmiller et al. (2020) found that student behavior, motivation, and socio-emotional factors influence teachers' perceptions and management strategies, which in turn affect academic performance. Poorly managed classrooms often lead to reduced instructional time and lower student engagement, ultimately impacting grades.

Furthermore, Isma'il and Lukman (2022) highlighted that instructional support and structured learning environments significantly enhance student performance. The present findings reinforce the idea that classroom management is not merely about discipline but is closely tied to academic success.

Although classroom management challenges account for a relatively small portion of the variance in academic performance (1.5%), the statistically significant negative relationship suggests that improving classroom management practices can contribute to better learner outcomes.

However, the low R^2 value also implies that academic performance is influenced by multiple other factors such as learner motivation, home environment, socioeconomic status, school leadership, and availability of instructional resources. Therefore, while strengthening classroom management through professional development, institutional support, and resource allocation is essential, a holistic approach is necessary to maximize academic achievement.

In conclusion, the findings affirm that reducing classroom management challenges can positively influence learners' academic performance, even if the effect is modest, and support the broader literature emphasizing the central role of effective classroom practices in educational success.

Part IV. Intervention Plan to Address Teachers' Classroom Management Challenges

The Intervention Plan titled "Addressing Classroom Management Challenges for Effective Teaching in San Andres District" is designed to address the multidimensional classroom management challenges faced by teachers. It responds to findings indicating that disruptive student behavior, inconsistent rules and discipline, limited teacher preparedness, inadequate resources, and low learner motivation negatively impact instructional effectiveness and academic performance. The program targets 266 Grades 1–6 teachers in San Andres District through a structured June–August professional development schedule. Interactive workshops, collaborative planning sessions, microteaching, classroom layout optimization, and role-playing scenarios form the core strategies for skills development. SMART objectives guide each component, ensuring that participants can demonstrate knowledge and application of proactive classroom management, consistent discipline practices, differentiated instruction, and culturally responsive pedagogy. Monitoring and evaluation are embedded throughout the program using classroom observations, self-assessments, peer reviews, and feedback mechanisms to track teacher performance and classroom outcomes. Expected results include reduced classroom disruptions, standardized rules and discipline, improved instructional delivery, optimized learning spaces, higher learner engagement, and stronger teacher-student relationships. Conflict management and cultural responsiveness are emphasized to promote inclusive, equitable, and harmonious learning environments. The plan also incorporates practical tools and resources, such as training manuals, lesson plan templates, checklists, and simulation exercises, to ensure immediate applicability in classrooms. Overall, this intervention seeks to enhance teacher competencies, foster effective classroom

management, and ultimately improve learners' academic achievement in the San Andres District.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn.

1. The teachers at San Andres District face pervasive and significant classroom management challenges across multiple domains. These challenges include enforcing rules, maintaining discipline, implementing effective teaching strategies, managing student behavior, optimizing instructional resources, organizing the physical environment, resolving conflicts, motivating learners, and fostering cultural inclusiveness. Collectively, these findings underscore the urgent need for targeted professional development, adequate resource allocation, and supportive school policies to enhance teacher competencies, promote inclusive and engaging learning environments, and improve overall student outcomes.
2. The learners in San Andres District generally demonstrate a Very Satisfactory academic performance. However, targeted interventions are necessary to support learners with lower scores and ensure equitable learning outcomes across the student population.
3. Classroom Management Challenges Faced by Teachers have a statistically significant, albeit modest, negative effect on learners' academic performance. This indicates that increased difficulties in managing classrooms are associated with lower General Weighted Averages, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis for these variables.
4. The proposed Intervention Plan is a comprehensive, targeted initiative designed to equip teachers with the skills, strategies, and support necessary to effectively manage classrooms. It aims to foster inclusive and engaging learning environments and ultimately improve learners' academic performance in the San Andres District.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Since the finding reveals that there are teachers generally experience classroom management practices at a high level. The Department of Education and school administrators may provide ongoing, targeted professional development programs, such as the proposed Intervention Plan initiative, including workshops, coaching, and mentoring to strengthen teachers' classroom management and culturally responsive teaching competencies.
2. Aligning from the findings that academic performance data of the learners in the district, inclusivity and equity will be essential in sustaining and improving

learner achievement across all grade levels and so, schools may ensure adequate, updated, and culturally relevant instructional materials, flexible classroom layouts, and teaching aids by establishing a district-level materials repository and allocating MOOE funds for procurement and development.

3. Findings affirm that reducing classroom management challenges faced by teachers can positively influence learners' academic performance, therefore, teachers may identify learners performing in the Fairly Satisfactory range and implement remedial programs, small-group instruction, and personalized strategies to address learning gaps and promote equitable academic outcomes.
4. By promoting a well managed, inclusive, and productive educational environment across the San Andres District, school leaders may establish clear and consistent policies on discipline, classroom management, and inclusivity, complemented by mentoring, administrative support, and regular monitoring to empower teachers and foster productive learning environments. Also, the proposed Intervention Plan is recommended for implementation to address classroom management challenges faced by teachers.
5. Since the study focus only in San Andres District, similar studies may be conducted in other districts, incorporating additional variables such as school climate, parental involvement, socio-economic factors, and teacher self-efficacy to further validate findings and explain the remaining variance in learners' academic performance.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study strictly adhered to ethical standards to ensure the protection, dignity, and rights of all participants involved. Prior to data collection, approval was secured from the appropriate education authorities, including the Division Superintendent, district supervisor, and school heads. Informed consent was obtained from all teacher respondents, while parental consent was sought for learner participation, ensuring that involvement in the study was voluntary and free from coercion. Participants were fully informed about the purpose, procedures, and significance of the study, as well as their right to refuse participation or withdraw at any time without penalty. Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained by using codes instead of names and securely storing all collected data. The information gathered was used solely for academic and research purposes and was not disclosed to any unauthorized individuals. The study also ensured that no physical, emotional, or psychological harm was inflicted on participants. Sensitive questions were handled with care, and respondents were given the option to skip items they were uncomfortable answering. Ethical principles of beneficence, respect for persons, and justice were observed throughout the research process. Furthermore, the study complied with institutional ethical guidelines and

relevant educational policies to ensure integrity and credibility in all stages of the research.

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